

P! GALERIE
"OBJETS BRUTS"

BALKRISHNA DOSHI
BATTISTA AND GINO GIUDICI
BRUNO REY
CHARLOTTE PERRIAND
DONALD JUDD
EILEEN GRAY
EULIE CHOWDHURY
GEORGE NAKASHIMA
GERRIT RIETVELD
HANS EICHENBERGERG
JEAN PROUVÉ
JEET MALHOTRA
LE CORBUSIER
LINA BO BARDI
MARCEL BREUER
MIGUEL FISAC
OSCAR NIEMEYER
PEDJA HADŽI-MANOVIĆ
PIERRE JEANNERET
RICARDO LEGORRETA
TOM STRALA
WILLY GUHL

ARCHIVE
DOCUMENT
FOUNDATION

P! GALERIE
CURATED BY PEDJA HADŽI-MANOVIĆ

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SEATS
SORTED BY DATE:

		[1920S]
1922	MARCEL BREUER	"LATTENSTUHL TI-1A"
1923	GERRIT RIETVELD	"ROOD-BLAUWE STOEL"
		[1930S]
1932	EILEEN GRAY	"SAFARI"
1938	MARCEL BREUER	"WB 301"
		[1940S]
1944	GEORGE NAKASHIMA	"GRASS-SEATED CHAIR"
1946	BATTISTA, GINO GIUDICI	"LIDO"
		[1950S]
1950		
1951	JEAN PROUVÉ	"MÉTROPOLE 305"
	GERRIT RIETVELD	"BERLIJNSE STOEL"
1953	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-01-C"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-04-A"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-06-A"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-08-A"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-30-A"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-30-C"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-30-D"
	LINA BO BARDI	"ARMCHAIR"
	MIGUEL FISAC	"TORO"
1954	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-38-B"
	WILLY GUHL	"STRANDSTUHL"
1955	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-10-A"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-18-A"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-20-A"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-24-A"

	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-28-A"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-28-B"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-28-D"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-29-A"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-32-C"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-36-A"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-36-B"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-45-A"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-45-A/B"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-59-A"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-59-B"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-59-D"
	LE CORBUSIER	"LC/PJ-SI-41-A"
	LE CORBUSIER	"LC/PJ-SI-41-B"
	LE CORBUSIER	"LC/PJ-SI-42-A"
	LE CORBUSIER	"LC/PJ-SI-42-B"
	LINA BO BARDI	"DIVA"
1956		
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"RARE"
1958		
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-25-A"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-25-E"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-32-A"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-32-B"
1959		
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-07-A"
		[1960S]
1960		
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-48-A"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-48-B"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-49-A"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-51-A"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-53-A"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-53-E"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-54-A"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-60-A"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-61-A"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-62-A"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-SOFA"
1963		
	GERRIT RIETVELD	"STELTMAN STOEL"
1965		
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-26-A"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-26-C"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-28-C"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-SI-35-A"
		[1970S]
1970		
	OSCAR NIEMEYER	"ALTA"
	HANS EICHENBERGER	"ANTI"
1972		
	RICARDO LEGORRETA	"VALLARTA"

1980 DONALD JUDD "NO 1 CHAIR" [1980S]

2005 TOM STRALA "KALAHARI"
TOM STRALA "KALAHARIO" [2000S]

2016 TOM STRALA "SF-1" [2010S]

2020 TOM STRALA "CHOUX 1"
TOM STRALA "CHOUX 3" [2020S]

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CONTENT BREAKDOWN:
2 CENTURIES
10 DECADES
13 AUTHORS
71 OBJECTS

GERRIT RIETVELD

"BERLIJNSE STOEL"

CA. 1923 - 1951

CHAIR

DE BILT

GERRIT RIETVELD

"STELTMAN STOEL"

CA. 1963

CHAIR

DE BILT

RICARDO LEGORRETA

"VALLARTA"

1972

CHAIR

TOLUCA

GEORGE NAKASHIMA

"GRASS-SEATED CHAIR"

1944

CHAIR

PENNSYLVANIA

JEAN PROUVÉ

"MÉTROPOLE 305"

1950

CHAIR

CITÉ CANSADO

MARCEL BREUER

"WB 301"

1938 - 1939

CHAIR

RÜTI

MARCEL BREUER

"LATTENSTUHL TI-1A"

1922 - 1924

SLATTED CHAIR

WEIMAR

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-25-E"

1958 - 1959

STUDENT CHAIR

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-25-A"

1958 - 1959

STUDENT CHAIR

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-28-B"

1955 - 1956

ARMCHAIR

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-28-A"

1955 - 1956

ARMCHAIR WITH FLOATING
BACKREST

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-28-D"

1955 - 1956

ARMCHAIR

CHANDIGARH

EULIE CHOWDHURY
PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-51-A"

1952-1956 AND 1960

LIBRARY CHAIR

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-54-A"

CA. 1960

BOX CHAIR

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-20-A"

1955 - 1960

CLERK'S CHAIR

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-06-A"

CA. 1953

CHAIR

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-53-A"

1960

CHAIR

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-26-C"

1960

WRITING CHAIR

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-26-A"

1960

WRITING CHAIR

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-53-E"

1960

WRITING CHAIR

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-46-A"

1960

CHAIR

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-30-A"

1953 - 1954

COMMITTEE CHAIR

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-30-C"

1953 - 1954

COMMITTEE CHAIR

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-30-D"

1953 - 1954

COMMITTEE CHAIR

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-32-C"

CA. 1955

UPHOLSTERED EASYCHAIR

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-28-C"

CA. 1960

UPHOLSTERED CHAIR

CHANDIGARH

DONALD JUDD

"NO 1 CHAIR"

1984

CHAIR

ZURICH

BATTISTA AND GINO GIUDICI "LIDO"

1946

LOUNGE SUN CHAIR

LOCARNO

TOM STRALA

"KALAHARIO"

5 OF 50

2005

CHAIR

ZURICH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"RARE"

CA. 1956

ARMCHAIR

CHANDIGARH

WILLY GUHL

"STRANDSTUHL"

1954

LOUNGE CHAIR

ZURICH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-62-A"

CA. 1960

ARMCHAIR

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-10-A"

CA. 1955

DEMONTABLE CHAIR

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-07-A"

1959

ARMCHAIR

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-04-A"

CA. 1953

EASYCHAIR

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-01-C"

CA. 1953

ARMCHAIR

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-61-A"

CA. 1960

EASYCHAIR

CHANDIGARH

LINA BO BARDI

"ARMCHAIR"

CA. 1953

ARMCHAIR

SÃO PAULO

MIGUEL FISAC

"TORO"

CA. 1950

ARMCHAIR

MADRID

GERRIT RIETVELD

"ROOD-BLAUWE STOEL"

CA. 1923

ARMCHAIR

DE BILT

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-48-A"

1960

UPHOLSTERED EASYCHAIR

CHANDIGARH

EILEEN GRAY

"SAFARI CHAIR"

1932

ARMCHAIR

ROQUEBRUNE - CAP - MARTIN

HANS EICHENBERGERG

"ANTI"

1970

LOUNGE CHAIR

ZURICH

OSCAR NIEMEYER

"ALTA"

1970

LOUNGE CHAIR AND OTTOMAN

PARIS

LINA BO BARDI

"DIVA"

CA. 1955

FOLDABLE CHAISE LONGUE

SÃO PAULO

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-48-B"

1960

UPHOLSTERED SOFA

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-32-A"

1958 - 1959

UPHOLSTERED EASYCHAIR

CHANDIGARH

TOM STRALA

"SF-1"

1 OF 50

2016

SOFA

ZURICH

TOM STRALA

"CHOUX 1"

2020

UPHOLSTERED ARMCHAIR

ZURICH

TOM STRALA

"CHOUX 3"

2020

UPHOLSTERED SOFA

ZURICH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-32-B"

1958 - 1959

UPHOLSTERED SOFA

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"LC/PJ-SI-42-B"

CA. 1955

HIGH COURT SOFA

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"LC/PJ-SI-42-A"

CA. 1955

HIGH COURT ARMCHAIR

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-36-A"

CA. 1955

UPHOLSTERED EASYCHAIR

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-36-B"

CA. 1955

UPHOLSTERED SOFA

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET
LE CORBUSIER

"LC/PJ-SI-41-A"

1955 - 1956

ADVOCATE AND PRESS CHAIR

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-36-B"

CA. 1955

ADVOCATE AND PRESS SOFA

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-38-B"

1954 - 1955

UPHOLSTERED SOFA

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-45-A/B"

1955 - 1956

SOFA SET

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-45-A"

1955 - 1956

ARMCHAIR

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-59-A"

1955

KANGAROO CHAIR

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-59-B"

1955 / 1964

KANGAROO SOFA

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-59-D"

CA. 1955

KANGAROO CHAIR

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-60-A"

CA. 1960

LOUNGE CHAIR

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-18-A"

1955 - 1960

ARMLESS CHAIR

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-08-A"

CA. 1953

ARMLESS EASYCHAIR

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-35-A"

CA. 1960

ARMLESS EASYCHAIR

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-SOFA"

CA. 1961

CANE SOFA

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-49-A"

1960 - 1961

THEATER CHAIR

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-29-A"

1955 - 1956

ARMCHAIR

CHANDIGARH

TOM STRALA

"KALAHARI"

1/1, PROTOTYPE

2005

CHAIR

ZURICH

TESTAMENT
RELIC
COLLECTION

P! GALERIE
CURATED BY PEDJA HADŽI-MANOVIĆ

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STOOLS
SORTED BY DATE:

1947 [1940S]
CHARLOTTE PERRIAND "BERGER"
CHARLOTTE PERRIAND "BERGER"
CHARLOTTE PERRIAND "SANDOZ"

1953 [1950S]
LE CORBUSIER "STOOL"

1954
LE CORBUSIER "STOOL"

1955
PIERRE JEANNERET "PJ-SI-24-A"
PIERRE JEANNERET "PJ-SI-34-A"
PIERRE JEANNERET "PJ-SI-40-B"
PIERRE JEANNERET "PJ-SI-67-A"
PIERRE JEANNERET "PJ-SI-68-A"

1959
LE CORBUSIER "LC-14"

1960 [1960S]
PIERRE JEANNERET "PJ-SI-55-A"
PIERRE JEANNERET "PJ-SI-57-A"
PIERRE JEANNERET "PJ-SI-58-A"
PIERRE JEANNERET "PJ-SI-66-A"

1965
PIERRE JEANNERET "PJ-SI-21-A"
PIERRE JEANNERET "PJ-SI-21-C HS"
PIERRE JEANNERET "PJ-SI-22-A"
PIERRE JEANNERET "PJ-SI-29-E"

2005 [2000S]
TOM STRALA "KALAHOCK"

BENCHES + DAYBEDS
SORTED BY DATE:

1936 [1930S]
JEAN PROUVÉ "RED DAYBED"

JEAN PROUVÉ "DAYBED" [1950S]
1951 JEAN PROUVÉ "SCAL-450"
1955 PIERRE JEANNERET "PJ-SI-33-C"
PIERRE JEANNERET "PJ-SI-33-E"
1955 PIERRE JEANNERET "PJ-L-02-A"
PIERRE JEANNERET "PJ-L-05-A"
1957 PIERRE JEANNERET "PJ-L-12-A"
PIERRE JEANNERET "PJ-L-12-B"

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CONTENT BREAKDOWN:
2 CENTURIES
5 DECADES
5 AUTHORS
29 OBJECTS

TOM STRALA

"KALAHOCK"

2/5

2005

STOOL

ZURICH

CHARLOTTE PERRIAND

"SANDOZ"

CA. 1947

STOOL

LES ARCS

CHARLOTTE PERRIAND

"STOOL"

CA. 1965

STOOL

LES ARCS

CHARLOTTE PERRIAND

"BERGER"

CA. 1947

STOOL

LES ARCS

CHARLOTTE PERRIAND

"BERGER"

CA. 1947

STOOL

LES ARCS

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-66-A"

1960

LOW STOOL

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-24-A"

1955 - 1956

SQUARE STOOL

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-55-A"

CA. 1960

LOW STOOL

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-57-A"

CA. 1960

LOW STOOL

CHANDIGARH

LE CORBUSIER

"STOOL"

1953 - 1954

HIGH STOOL

AHMEDABAD

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-58-A"

CA. 1960

HIGH STOOL

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-22-A"

1965 - 1966

ROUND STOOL WITH WOODEN SEAT

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-21-A"

1965 - 1966

ROUND CANE STOOL

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-21-C HIGH STOOL"

1965 - 1966

ROUND HIGH STOOL WITH
WOODEN SEAT

CHANDIGARH

LE CORBUSIER

"LC-14"

CA. 1959

BOX STOOL

ROQUEBRUNE - CAP - MARTIN

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-67-A"

CA. 1955

CUBE STOOL

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-40-B"

1955 - 1956

UPHOLSTERED STOOL

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-34-A"

1955 - 1956

CANE STOOL

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-68-A"

1955 - 1956

STOOL

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-29-E"

CA. 1965

LOW STOOL

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-33-C"

1955 - 1956

CANE BENCH

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-SI-33-E"

1955 - 1956

SLATTED BENCH

CHANDIGARH

JEAN PROUVÉ

"SCAL-450"

1951

DAYBED

CANSADO

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-L-12-A"

1957 - 1958

DAYBED

CHANDIGARH

JEAN PROUVÉ

"DAYBED"

1951

DAYBED

CANSADO

JEAN PROUVÉ

"RED DAYBED"

CA. 1936

DAYBED

CANSADO

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-L-05-A"

CA. 1955 - 1956

DAYBED

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-L-02-A"

CA. 1955 - 1956

DAYBED

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-L-12-B"

CA. 1957 - 1958

DAYBED

CHANDIGARH

INHERITANCE
FILE
REGISTRY

2026
CURATED BY PEDJA HADŽI-MANOVIĆ

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TABLES / DESKS
SORTED BY DATE:

[1950S]

1952	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-TB-04-A"
1953	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-TB-03-A"
1954	CHARLOTTE PERRIAND PIERRE JEANNERET	"BENCH" "PJ-TA-09-A"
1955	LE CORBUSIER PIERRE JEANNERET	"LC/PJ-BU-01-A" "PJ-TAT-08-A"
1956	PIERRE JEANNERET PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-DESK" "PJ-TAT-05-A"
1957	LE CORBUSIER PIERRE JEANNERET PIERRE JEANNERET	"LC-TAT-07-A" "PJ-BU-02-A" "PJ-BU-16-A"
1958	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-BU-14-A"
1959	PIERRE JEANNERET PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-TA-04-A" "PJ-TA-04-B"
1960	LE CORBUSIER PIERRE JEANNERET PIERRE JEANNERET	"LC/BD-01-A" "PJ-BU-06-A" "PJ-BU-08-A" "PJ-BU-08-B" "PJ-BU-13-A" "PJ-BU-19-A" "PJ-L-09-A" "PJ-TA-01-A/B/C" "PJ-TA-11-A" "PJ-TA-12-A" "PJ-TB-05-A"
1961	PIERRE JEANNERET PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-TA-05-A" "PJ-TB-03-C"
1963	PIERRE JEANNERET PIERRE JEANNERET	"LC/PJ-TAT-14-A" "PJ-TAT-13-D"
1979	LEHNI	"SIDE TABLEE"

[1970S]

[2000S]

2007	TOM STRALA	"BARTOK"
2011	TOM STRALA	"NEW YORK TIMES"
2013	TOM STRALA	"NEW YORK TIMES II"
2021	TOM STRALA	"TS-290KG"

[2010S]
[2020S]

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CONTENT BREAKDOWN:
2 CENTURIES
6 DECADES
5 AUTHORS
34 OBJECTS

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-DESK"

1956

DESK

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-BU-02-A"

1957 - 1958

DESK

CHANDIGARH

LE CORBUSIER
PIERRE JEANNERET

"LC/PJ-BU-01-A"

CA. 1954 - 1955

CURVED EXECUTIVE DESK

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-BU-13-A"

1960

DESK WITH STORAGE

CHANDIGARH

BALKRISHNA DOSHI
LE CORBUSIER

"LC/BD-01-A"

CA. 1960

CONSOLE DESK

AHMEDABAD

LE CORBUSIER

"LC-TAT-07-A"

1957 - 1958

MINISTER'S DESK

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-BU-14-A"

1958 - 1960

EXECUTIVE DESK

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-BU-16-A"

1957 - 1958

DESK

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-BU-06-A"

CA. 1960

ADMINISTRATIVE DESK

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-BU-19-A"

CA. 1960

ADMINISTRATIVE DESK

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-TA-12-A"

CA. 1960

DESK

CHANDIGARH

CHARLOTTE PERRIAND

"FORME LIBRE"

1957

TABLE

BRAZZAVILLE

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-TAT-08-A"

1955 - 1956

TABLE

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-TA-01-A/B/C"

1960 - 1961

CONFERENCE TABLE

CHANDIGARH

LE CORBUSIER
PIERRE JEANNERET

"LC/PJ-TAT-14-A"

1963 - 1964

BOOMERANG TABLE

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-TA-04-B"

1959 - 1960

SQUARE TABLE

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-TA-04-A"

1959 - 1960

SQUARE TABLE

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-TA-05-A"

1961 - 1962

SQUARE TABLE

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-TA-11-A"

1960

COLLAPSIBLE DESK

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-BU-08-A"

CA. 1960

STUDENT DESK

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-BU-08-B"

CA. 1960

WORKING DESK

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-TAT-05-A"

1956 - 1957

COLLAPSIBLE CONSOLE

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-TAT-13-D"

1963

CONSOLE

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-TA-09-A"

CA. 1954

JUDGE LUNCH TABLE

CHANDIGARH

TAOM STRALA

"BARTOK"

2 OF 25

2007 - 2008

SIDE TABLE

ZURICH

CHARLOTTE PERRIAND

"BENCH"

CA. 1954

BENCH

CANSADO

TOM STRALA

"NEW YORK TIMES"

01 OF 25

2011

SIDE TABLE

ZURICH

TOM STRALA

"NEW YORK TIMES II"

01 OF 25

2013

SIDE TABLE

ZURICH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-TB-03-C"

1961

TRIANGULAR SIDE TABLE

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET
CHARLOTTE PERRIAND

"PJ-TB-04-A"

1952-56, 1960

ROUND SIDE TABLE

CHANDIGARH

TAOM STRALA

"TS-290KG"

2021

SIDE TABLE

ZURICH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-L-09-A"

CA. 1960

CANED BED /
COFFEE TABLE

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-TB-05-A"

CA. 1960

SIDE TABLE

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-TB-03-A"

CA. 1953

TRIANGULAR SIDE TABLE

CHANDIGARH

LEHNI

"SIDE TABLE"

1979

SIDE TABLE

ZURICH

CATALOGUE
ARTIFACT
DATA

2026
CURATED BY PEDJA HADŽI-MANOVIĆ

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STORAGE
SORTED BY DATE:

		[1950S]
1950	CHARLOTTE PERRIAND	"BAHUT-5"
1955	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-R-09-A"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-R-11-A"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-R-07-A"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-R-14-A"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-R-23-A"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-R-27-A"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-R-27-B"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-R-26-A"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-R-26-A"
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-R-04-A"
1958	CHARLOTTE PERRIAND	"BAHUT-3"
	CHARLOTTE PERRIAND	"BAHUT-4"
	CHARLOTTE PERRIAND	"NUAGE"
		[1960S]
1963	GERRIT RIETVELD	"ELLING"
		[2000S]
2009	PEDJA HADŽI-MANOVIĆ	"3-7-3"

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CONTENT BREAKDOWN:
2 CENTURY
3 DECADES
4 AUTHORS
16 OBJECTS

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-R-04-A"

1960

DOUBLE-SIDED BOOKCASE

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-R-26-A"

SOLID TEAK, ALUMINIUM

1960

BOOKCASE FOR PERIODICALS

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-R-26-A"

SOLID TEAK, TEAK VENEER

1960

BOOKCASE FOR PERIODICALS

CHANDIGARH

CHARLOTTE PERRIAND

"NUAGE"

1958

WALL-MOUNTED SHELF WITH
THREE LEVELS

CANSADO

CHARLOTTE PERRIAND

"BAHUT-5"

1950

BUFFET WITH FIVE SLIDING DOORS

CANSADO

CHARLOTTE PERRIAND

"BAHUT-4"

1958

BUFFET WITH FOUR SLIDING DOORS

CANSADO

CHARLOTTE PERRIAND

"BAHUT-3"

1958

BUFFET WITH THREE SLIDING DOORS

CANSADO

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-R-14-A"

1957 - 1958

BUFFET WITH FOUR DOORS

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-R-09-A"

1955 - 1956

SIDE TABLE

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-R-11-A"

1955 - 1956

SIDEBOARD WITH DRAWERS

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-R-07-A"

CA. 1960 - 1961

PORTABLE BOOK RACK

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-R-23-A"

1957 - 1958

LINEN CHEST

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-R-27-A"

1957 - 1958

FILE RACK WITH SIX HOLES

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-R-27-B"

1957 - 1958

FILE RACK WITH FIVE HOLES

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-R-16-A"

1958

SCULPTURAL BUFFET

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-R-13-A"

1958

BUFFET WITH GLASS DOORS

CHANDIGARH

GERRIT RIETVELD

"ELLING"

1919 / 1974

BUFFET

DE BILT

PEDJA HADŽI-MANOVIĆ

"3-7-3"

2011

BUFFET

BELGRADE

DOSSIER
PROVENANCE
INTEGRITY

2026
CURATED BY PEDJA HADŽI-MANOVIĆ

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LAMPS / CARPETS / MISCELLANEOUS
SORTED BY DATE:

LAMPS

1950			[1950S]
	CHARLOTTE PERRIAND	"CP-1"	[1960S]
1960			
	LE CORBUSIER	"LC-III"	
1961			
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-LU-04-B"	
1963			
	LE CORBUSIER	"LC-LU-02-A"	[2000S]
2005			
	TOM STRALA	"BOURGEOISIE 3"	
2007			
	TOM STRALA	"POMPIDU 1"	
	TOM STRALA	"POMPIDU 2"	[2010S]
2010			
	TOM STRALA	"CALMARES"	
	TOM STRALA	"CALMARES II"	
2011			
	TOM STRALA	"ANIMAL FARM 2"	
2016			
	TOM STRALA	"CALMARES III"	
	TOM STRALA	"CHAOS"	
	TOM STRALA	"SF-1"	[2020S]
2024			
	ALTHERR / WEISS	"EMPIRE STATE"	
	ALTHERR / WEISS	"RAW"	
	ALTHERR / WEISS	"SUCCESSION"	
2025			
	TOM STRALA	"DE MAYO"	

CARPETS

1950			[1950S]
		"AIT ELFERAHE"	
		"BENI OUARRAIN"	
		"BENI OUARRAIN"	[1960S]
1960			
		"BENI OUARRAIN"	
1965			

"OUKAIMEDEN"
[1970S]

1970

"MEKNES AREA"

MISCELLANEOUS

1954			[1950S]
	BRUNO REY	"PLANTER"	
1957			
	PIERRE JEANNERET	"PJ-DIVERS-01"	

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CONTENT BREAKDOWN:
2 CENTURY
6 DECADES
6 AUTHORS
23 OBJECTS

TOM STRALA

"ANIMAL FARM 2"

5 OF 25

2011 - 2015

FLOOR LAMP

ZURICH

CHARLOTTE PERRIAND

"CP-1"

CA. 1950

WALL LIGHTS

LES ARCS

FLOOR LAMP

ZURICH

WALL LAMP

ZURICH

LAMP

ZURICH

LAMP

ZURICH

LIGHT FIXTURE

ZURICH

LIGHT FIXTURE

ZURICH

FLOOR LAMP

ZURICH

FLOOR LAMP

ZURICH

LAMP

ZURICH

FLOOR LAMP

ZURICH

LE CORBUSIER

"LC-III"

1960

WALL LAMP

AHMEDABAD

TOM STRALA

"CALMARES III"

07 OF 50

2016

FLOOR LAMP

ZURICH

LE CORBUSIER

"LC-LU-02-A"

1963 - 1964

FLOOR LAMP

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET
JEET MALHOTRA
EULIE CHOWDHURY

"PJ-LU-04-B"

1955 - 1956

FLOOR LAMP

CHANDIGARH

LE CORBUSIER

"LC-EA-05-A"

1952 - 1956

VENTILATION SHUTTERS

CHANDIGARH

LE CORBUSIER

"LC-WITNESS BOX"

1955

WITNESS STAND

CHANDIGARH

PIERRE JEANNERET

"PJ-DIVERS-01"

1957 - 1958

SCREEN WITH 3 PANELS

CHANDIGARH

BRUNO REY

"PLANTER"

1954

PLANTER

ETERNIT

"BENI OUARRAIN"

CA. 1960

RUG

MIDDLE ATLAS

"MEKNES AREA"

CA. 1970

RUG

MIDDLE ATLAS

"BENI OUARRAIN"

CA. 1960

RUG

MIDDLE ATLAS

"BENI OUARRAIN"

CA. 1950

RUG

MIDDLE ATLAS

"AIT ELFERAHE"

CA. 1950

RUG

MIDDLE ATLAS

"OUKAIMEDEN"

CA. 1965

RUG

MIDDLE ATLAS

